

Pharmaceutical Sector Digitalization

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Abstract:- In today's climate, "digital" is become an essential part of almost everything. All sectors would move more quickly into the digital era. The pharmaceutical industry has not yet fully adopted online marketing, with the exception of the webpage. Currently, the country is facing several difficulties. In terms of marketing, the pharmaceutical sector dominates all other sectors. This generation is producing more medications. Through social media platforms and e-commerce websites, businesses are marketing themselves online. Customers can so make online purchases. While some businesses are having trouble realising all the advantages of digital, others have incorporated it into every aspect of their marketing strategy. Pharmaceutical businesses will take part in these campaigns to promote their brands. Influencers always searching for fresh approaches to promote their brands. An influence who is popular on social networks and has had the condition before can be engaged to effectively pique Covid patients' interest, for example, if a pharmaceutical company contacts Covid patients. Influencers may be useful when it comes to pharmaceuticals or medical supplies. On the other side, all of the businesses make prescription medications, which cannot be bought online, therefore they are unable to offer their goods online. YouTube, Daily Motion, Instagram, Twitter, and Facebook were used to interact with clients. E-commerce and online marketing are made simpler by the Northeast-based Quantum Pharmaceuticals and The Specials Lab, which both sell unusual pharmaceuticals online. (Il'ino vaetal.,2021)

The development of every manufacturing industry's production process requires the adoption of digital technology. As a result of the digitalization process, there is an increasing usage of robotics, automation, and computerization, which reduces costs, increases production and efficiency, and increases adaptability. The pharmaceutical industry has been resistive to digitization because of ignorance and the difficulty of the research and production processes involved. In spite of this, it is obvious that the pharmaceutical industry has to become digital since there is a growing need for both old and new medications.

This article gives a general overview of the essential elements of the pharmaceutical industry's digitization, discusses both the advantages of the process, and puts a particular emphasis on workable solutions for further digital implementation.

Keywords: *Pharmaceutical marketing, digital marketing ,digital marketing strategies, pharma, social media.*

I. INTRODUCTION

With projected global sales of \$1228.45 billion by 2020, the pharmaceutical industry is one of the fastest-growing economic sectors. Since 2017, the pharmaceutical sector has expanded at a rate of 5.8% each year. The pharmaceutical industry generated 1143 billion dollars in revenue in 2017, and 1462 billion dollars are expected to be generated by 2021. (Crawley, 2012). The core of the sector, according to the International Trade Administration, is "the research, development, manufacture, and marketing of pharmaceuticals and biologicals for human or veterinary use." Innovations management et al., Henkel. Digitalization is the utilisation of data from systems integration, connected devices, and other sources to more accurately predict and forecast consumer demand and enhance supply chain effectiveness. (Il'ino vaetal.,2021)

Pharmaceutical Industry 4.0 will enable augmentation production in the future, enabling, among other things, targeted 3D printing of treatments, additive manufacturing, and customised medication. (Reinhardt et al.,2021; Hariryet al., 2021).

Even while some companies are technologically progressive, there aren't many solid case studies of digitization in the pharmaceutical sector, which makes it difficult to employ. The pharmaceutical industry is not a good fit for online marketing. While online advertising in banking, professional services, manufacturing, and business services flourished, the pharmaceutical industry was constrained by cautious behaviour and unclear legislation. On the other hand, Medical communities have grown to accommodate doctors' healthcare professionals' (HCP), key opinion leaders' (KOL), and the larger medical establishment's increased use of the internet, social media, and online information. This has prompted pharmaceutical companies to expand in and test content marketing strategies in accordance with industry standards. This is amongst the most effective marketing strategies, which is surprising. Utilizing social media, pharmaceutical businesses may improve their brand image. (Klunko,2020)

II. DIGITALIZATION IN INDIAN PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

In India's pharmaceutical sector, digital marketing is still in its infancy. Pharmaceutical firms are using technology to better inform patients about their diseases and monitor their progress. Giving doctors details on the patient's condition and any negative side effects from the drug may also be beneficial. The communication between doctors and patients concerning certain medical conditions

is also made simpler by these digital platforms.

The effective and affordable techniques of digital marketing have simplified the planning of public awareness campaigns, advertising, and mass reach. The use of pharmaceuticals in medicine is widespread. Heart disease and excessive blood pressure are more common than ever in developed countries. Infectious diseases including typhoid, TB, and a number of other ailments are widespread in underdeveloped countries. To keep up with the changes that digital technology has brought us, pharmaceutical companies are working extremely hard. The use of digital marketing in this industry in recent years has allowed businesses to take a fresh approach for interacting with patients, caregivers, and patients.

Numerous technologies, such as cloud computing, mobile communications, advanced analytics, and the internet, are transforming the healthcare industry. Even though the majority of Indian organisations have limited their usage to corporate image establishment, therapy updates, minimal diet advice, nutrition, and exercise, nutraceuticals have an active distribution network with just a small number of businesses focusing on OTC items. The use of digital marketing in this industry in recent years has allowed businesses to take a fresh approach for interacting with patients, caregivers, and patients.

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III. CURRENT SCENARIO AND CHALLENGES OF PHARMACEUTICAL INDUSTRY

The number of internet users worldwide is expected to reach 4.48 billion in 2019, with 560 million users in India and 802 million users in China, and the number is expected to continue to rise. This has significantly boosted a number of sectors in the digital age.

When compared to traditional marketing, digital marketing is a more time- and money-efficient way to involve customers in any firm. Pharmaceutical marketers may leverage data from digital marketing to develop more strategic connections with prescribers and doctors.

In spite of this, many businesses continue to have difficulty fully integrating digital into their overall company plan. The pharmaceutical industry has a variety of challenges when implementing digital marketing strategies, some of which are outlined here. (Nurgozhin&Sakipova,2021)

The Indian pharmaceutical business is undergoing unprecedented change as a result of the current situation and COVID-19. Due to panic buying during the lockdown, the current demand for medications is fairly strong across the nation. More than 9% more prescription drugs were sold

overall. Drugs used to treat diabetes, respiratory conditions, and cardiac therapy all had large increases of 12-23 percent in March. The demand for all other medicines is quite high nationwide. Many of the businesses witnessed a 20–30% boost in sales in only March. Due to an overwhelming amount of demand on the domestic market, the Indian government first banned the export of 13 essential pharmaceuticals, but this was later lifted. More digitization would have greatly improved this industry because it speeds up and streamlines the process. (Qodirov,2021)

The majority of businesses lack a clear plan for how they will employ digital marketing techniques due to a lack of corporate vision. The techniques are not widely acknowledged, recognised, or known. Good management is necessary to confirm the vision, define goals, and assess the operation's level of quality. Most businesses find it challenging to pinpoint the field force and marketing advocates who advance the digital pharmacy concept.

("Knowledge and awareness of cad cam surgical guide in digitalization of implants among dental practitioners.", 2020)

The pharmaceutical industry lacks bright people who want to lead digital change. To implement digital marketing within the company, employees need to be aware of both digital marketing and the challenges associated with digital adoption in the pharmaceutical business. A productive staff that is knowledgeable about both their sector and the emerging digital market is lacking in the majority of businesses.

Although some pharmaceutical businesses have started utilising digital channels and initiatives, most have been unable to develop a thorough digital strategy. Improved data made it easier to complete challenging analysis, yet the use of data in modern ways has caused a worldwide catastrophe. To maximise digital marketing, pharmaceutical marketers will mix data from many sources, use it in real-time, and take use of their expertise in the digital space. (Seredkina,2021)

Strict Requirements: Before beginning any digital activity, it's important to understand the regulations in each nation. Compared to other industries, life sciences marketing is subject to stricter rules. The pharmaceutical industry is required to abide by FDA and Federal Trade Commission (FTC) regulations regarding anything from privacy to original authoring. HIPAA, or the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act, is an abbreviation.

founded in 1996 to protect the privacy and security of medical data. In order to protect the confidentiality of medical information, the law makes it unlawful for advertising to use health data that is stored digitally. Due to incomplete risk information, the FDA requested that Novartis remove its Facebook portion of the leukaemia treatment drug Tassigna in a warning letter it wrote to the company in 2010. Because of the search restrictions, pharmaceutical companies have become more inventive. ("The digitalization decision",2021)

neglected websites Corporations in the biopharmaceutical industry aren't very active on social media. The "Web 1.0" technology is still in use by several pharmaceutical businesses. The pharmaceutical sector has selected a one-way data transfer technology that has undergone rigorous testing, is recognised by law, and is safe from outside intervention. These websites only provide

information that cannot be obtained by speaking directly with patients. Finding an outdated, unmaintained website by accident is worse than finding none at all. Effective human resources need to learn how to handle these situations. Doctors, pharmaceuticals, and consumer surveys After completing the survey which covered Mumbai and its neighboring region.

Place of practice:

Fig. 1

We discovered that the pharmacies sell 35.5 percent of their inventory without a prescription and 64.5 percent with one, allowing us to focus on these clients and facilitate their online purchases.

Do you sell it with prescription?

≈S

Fig. 2

Since most people consult doctors before purchasing a medication, targeting doctors is crucial, and medical representatives are the most crucial point of contact, training them to use digital platforms will enable MRs to interact with as many doctors and pharmacies as possible and promote the company's products.

Fig. 3

IV. DIFFERENT TYPES OF DIGITAL MARKETING

A. Search Engine Optimization:

The purpose of SEO is to raise a website's placement in Google search, which will bring in more visitors from search engines. In order to do this, SEO marketers hunt for terms and phrases consumers use to search for information online and also include them within their own content. Per the Moz's "Beginners Guide to SEO," SEO takes into account a host of variables, including the language used on your web pages, how other websites link to you online, and the layout of your website. According to Salary.com, an SEO expert may earn more than \$70,058 year. ("The strategic digitalization and market approaches in the pharmaceutical industry.", 2021)

B. Pay-per-click(PPC)

Pay-per-click (PPC) refers to sponsored search rankings and paid adverts. Because it is a limited-time sort of digital marketing, if you stop making payments, the advertisement will disappear. PPC is a strategy, like SEO, for boosting a business's internet search traffic.

Commercials that appear prior YouTube videos, at the top and sides of search results pages, when a user is browsing the web, and in mobile applications are all examples of pay-per-click advertising.

C. Content Marketing

Storytelling and knowledge exchange are used in content marketing to raise brand recognition. The intention is for the reader to take a move in the direction of becoming a client, such as asking for additional details, joining an email list, or completing a purchase. Content consists of blog entries, documents like white papers and e-books, streaming video, podcasts, and a lot more. In general, it should place more of an emphasis on adding value to the consumer than simply marketing the brand or attempting to sell something. Building a long-lasting, trustworthy relationship with your consumers that may lead to more than one purchase is the main goal of content marketing.

D. Email Marketing

Email is still one of the most efficient marketing strategies, claims Rogers, despite the rise of social media, smartphone applications, and other platforms. It could be used as a component of a content marketing plan to provide consumers with value before attempting to turn them into paying clients. The American Marketing Association claims that email marketing professionals are adept at not only creating engaging emails but also identifying the right audience outreach and monitoring consumer feedback.

E. E-Detailing

Still little is known about the Indian industry. A small number of companies control the majority of the Indian e-commerce market. Although the sales force first had their doubts about e-details, they became interested in whether online marketing would replace the traditional sales call. But most members discovered that using electronic details made their time with the representative more valuable. (Verba&Haidamaka, 2020)

F. Webinars/ECMES (electronic continuing medical education)

Hybrid meetings are events that mix real-world and online components. One of the biggest advancements in event planning, they also have enormous potential. Event planners and organising organisations will be able to improve the exposure of our gathering by live streaming it via streaming video, as well as those who are observing the conference online. One of the Indian pharmaceutical industry's most economical tactics is this one.

V. STRATEGIES THAT CAN BE USED/ADOPTED BY COMPANIES TO INCREASE THEIR DIGITAL WORLD PRESENCE

- **Create a new digital marketing organizational structure:** Make appointments for a digital marketing committee, an e-marketing strategy leader, and so on.
- **Introducing mobile apps:** The pharmaceutical industry has been hoping for the FDA to provide rules on medical applications for mobile devices. Prior to their immediate release, mobile applications help patients better understand their diagnosis and medications. Apps that enable more effective consumer direct marketing may offer in-depth knowledge of any medicine. Instead of focusing on illness treatment, pharmaceutical businesses would generate more income if they partnered with firms that could offer patient management applications, such as symptom and drug management.
- **Collaborative business model:** The pharmaceutical sector is expanding via collaboration with and well beyond its partners despite its conventional obstacles. Collaboration is possible in a variety of ways thanks to digital technology. Successful and effective medication discovery will be possible for workers. To enable smart test design, precision medicine, and other fields of medicine, Pfizer, for instance, has created a ground-breaking cloud-based clinical evidence platform to gather, evaluate, and show patient data within clinical trials and medical programming.
- **Sharing Extensive overtime data collected** on population studies typically go to waste if they are not examined. Results from the data should be published. The combination of point, mobile, and quantitative content will actually bring about change in the digital healthcare industry.
- **Ensure enough IT support:** To handle digital marketing issues, adequate IT help is essential. **Partnerships with firms** digital initiatives that address complimentary sickness aspects. For instance, firms that market anticoagulants for fibrillation may work with manufacturers of medical devices that employ remote evaluation and treatment to identify such patients. Digital marketing strategy is simple to put into practise.
- **Patient and healthcare provider services (HCPs):** Additionally, patient and medical provider services (HCPs) are expected to provide patients with digital services that might regularly assist patients with quality administration and monitoring by using additional software. Research and therapeutic strategies can also be aided by these services. As a further aid and means of demonstrating results, it joins partners from the greater healthcare community. Digitally enabled healthcare treatment, including applications or online platforms, or instructional materials related to a greater range, should be used to assist patients and HCPs coping with health issues. (Vermeer&Thomas,2020)
- Medical seminars should be held to inform and educate medical professionals and major organizational executives so they are completely up to speed on the latest business developments. Webinars' primary purpose is to give clients accurate, verified information so they can spread

the word about it.

- Training Medical Representatives Digital Knowledge
- Social media: A team of medical reps should reach out to customers every week via LinkedIn, WhatsApp, emails, etc. Both the company's brand recognition and the physicians' frequent updates would benefit from this.
- Online campaigns—Online campaigns, such as educational films, advertisements, posters, etc.—should be developed to specifically target doctors in order to raise brand awareness. This will enable you to reach the most consumers.
- We will give MRs the appropriate training because it is crucial to have professionally trained medical representatives. utilising modern technologies, teaching them how to engage clients and raise awareness
- We'll begin by seeking for new Skilled MRs with strong interpersonal, negotiating, and listening abilities. plus analytical abilities.
- After that, a training campaign will be conducted to polish their abilities and teach them new ones.
- Then, a training programme will be conducted in which their talents will be improved and new skills will be given to them, ultimately resulting in their upgrading.
- Then, a matrix will be presented to assist in evaluating the success of the MRs so that they can understand how they are going and where they need to improve

VI. CONCLUSION

The majority of people's time these days is spent on their smartphones, laptops, or tablets since they are so busy. technology-related devices According to the pharmaceutical industry, digital marketing is crucial. results of recent studies Digital commercialisation allows for quick company growth. It has made a name for itself as a potent marketing cornerstone, motivating and advancing activities that are far less difficult. Only a few digital marketing strategies are often used, and they have a narrow range of applications. Others are already doing it. On the other hand, it is easy to apply all types of digital marketing and may save a lot of money. There has been a huge investment of cash, time, effort, and passion. These revolutionary breakthroughs were pioneered by pharmaceutical businesses that are up to speed with the current digital environment. Such strategies were exclusively applied on blogs, Facebook pages, and LinkedIn accounts. despite the scant and poorly maintained data. We discovered the same thing in our investigation.

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